

Climate Change and the Future of Turkish Aquaculture Sector: Stakeholders' Perspective under the CERES Project Scenarios

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Objective: This study aims to investigate the opinions of Turkish aquaculture sector stakeholders on the possible impacts of climate change on the Turkish aquaculture sector. Stakeholders' opinions are gathered within the context of socio-political scenarios for the fishery and aquaculture sector in Europe. These socio-political scenarios are developed by the CERES (Climate Change and European Aquatic Resource) Project, with reference to IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) release scenarios.

Method: This study is conducted using data gathered from two stakeholder workshops. First workshop is jointly organized by Mersin University CERES Project Team and Elazığ Aquaculture Research Institute on May 4, 2017 in Elazığ, Turkey. Second workshop is jointly organized by Mersin University CERES Project Team and Kılıç Deniz Inc. on May 22, 2017 in Muğla. In these two workshops, first CERES Project, along with its aim and scope, is introduced. Then the four socio-political scenarios for the fishery and aquaculture sector in Europe are explained to the participants. These four socio-political scenarios, developed by the CERES Project, are namely World Markets, Global Sustainability, National Enterprise and Local Stewardship Scenarios. CERES Project defines the "possibility-space" of these scenarios with an axis representing "global to local" and an axis representing "sustainability to consumerism". After explaining these socio-political scenarios, participants are requested to fill-out a semi-structured questionnaire consisted of 12 questions to gather data on participants' opinions about the likelihood of these scenarios to occur in the future; possible impacts of climate change on the Turkish aquaculture sector and their strategies (if any) to manage the impacts of climate change. In these two workshops, total of 20 stakeholders (12 producers and 8 other types of stakeholders) are volunteered to participate in the questionnaire.

Results and Discussion: Analysis of the collected data shows that the most likely scenario in the future is the World Markets Scenario. 13 participants have foreseen this scenario as the most likely scenario, while 5 participants have foreseen the Global Sustainability Scenario and 2 participants have foreseen the National Enterprise Scenario as the most likely scenarios in the future. None of the participants has foreseen the Local Stewardship Scenario as the most likely scenario in the future. Analysis results also show that the majority of participants believe that the climate change will have negative impact on aquaculture sector. However, nearly no participant has any strategy in their mind to manage the impacts of climate change. Among very few, the most notable strategy is the government to take active part by arranging meetings with the sector, predicting the impacts of climate change and enacting necessary legal regulations.

Keywords: Climate change, aquaculture, CERES socio-political scenarios